

**EFFECTIVE HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT FOR SUSTAINABLE
MOTIVATION OF SECONDARY TEACHERS IN THE MVIILA DEPARTMENT,
SOUTHERN CAMEROON****Damaris Mireille Solange MBANG ASSALE**

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ABSTRACT

Human Resource Management (HRM) and career management present significant challenges for secondary school teachers. Current practices lack objectivity and are, at times, borderline deviant. This social context negatively impacts the sustainable motivation of secondary teachers in the Mvila Department. To establish the link between HRM and their sustainable motivation, a quantitative study was conducted. Findings from a sample of 113 teachers, analyzed using Pearson's correlation test, indicate that HR acquisition practices, stimulation practices, and development practices exert a strong negative influence on the sustainable motivation of secondary teachers in Mvila. These results confirm the existence of a direct relationship between current HRM practices and the long-term motivation of high school teachers in the Mvila region.

Keywords:

Sustainable motivation, Acquisition practices, Stimulation practices, Development practices.

1. INTRODUCTION

Human Resource Management (HRM) is defined as a comprehensive set of strategic practices designed to acquire, develop, and retain the human resources (HR) essential for an organization to achieve its objectives. Effective HRM, through a coherent overarching policy, mobilizes employee competencies by fostering sustained professional engagement, thereby transforming human capital into a sustainable competitive advantage. To this end, it is imperative to account for the specific characteristics of individuals and ensure an alignment between their evolving aspirations and organizational goals a balance that represents a significant challenge for modern managers (Martin, 2010).

The effectiveness of this function is closely linked to the strategic role of the Human Resources Department (HRD). The HRD must ensure that the most suitable person is placed in each position at the opportune time, while providing a work environment and training opportunities conducive to personal and professional fulfillment (Nkoulou, 2021). Within a context of social shifts and a growing demand for education, the effective management of teaching human resources (THR) has become imperative to attract candidates, motivate them, and ensure their retention within the educational system.

In the specific context of Cameroon, rigorous teacher management is crucial for aligning professional aspirations with national pedagogical objectives. However, empirical observations conducted in the Mvila Department reveal a concerning disconnect: teachers face salaries deemed unsatisfactory, a lack of clear career development plans, and persistent administrative "slowness" in the processing of their professional files.

Nevertheless, the State's financial commitments have shown steady growth. The annual budget allocation for the Ministry of Secondary Education (MINESEC) rose from 394 billion FCFA in 2019 to 584 billion FCFA in 2025 (Law No. 2018/022 and Law No. 2024/022). Despite this massive investment and the existence of a robust regulatory framework comprising the General Statute of the Public Service, the Special Statute for Civil Servants in the National Education Corps, and the National Development Strategy 2020-2030 (SND30) teacher dissatisfaction remains high.

The present study is motivated by this paradox of persistent demotivation. While short-term motivation is often observed following specific measures, it quickly diminishes, leading to professional disengagement. This lack of sustainable motivation is illustrated by the recurrence of strike actions, such as those led by the "On A Trop Supporté" (OTS, 2022) collective. Consequently, it is necessary to examine the adequacy of management tools

relative to field realities. This reflection leads to the following central research question: **What is the relationship between HRM practices and the sustainable motivation of secondary school teachers in the Mvila Department?**

2. THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework of this study is structured around McClelland's Theory of Needs, examined in relation to the concepts of sustainable motivation and Human Resource Management (HRM) practices (acquisition, stimulation, and development).

2.1. McClelland's Theory of Needs

David McClelland's theory (1950, 1961), also known as the Three Needs Theory, postulates that three fundamental needs influence human behavior in a professional environment (McClelland, 1987):

- **Need for Achievement:** Individuals seek to excel, embrace challenges, and attain ambitious goals (McClelland & Burnham, 1976). They are motivated by concrete success and the recognition of their efforts (Spangler, 1992).
- **Need for Affiliation:** This reflects the desire to establish harmonious interpersonal relationships and values collaboration and group belonging (Boyatzis, 1973; McAdams, 1980).
- **Need for Power:** This is manifested by the desire to influence others (Winter, 1973). McClelland (1975) distinguishes between **personal power** (individual dominance) and **institutional power**, the latter being focused on achieving collective goals and organizing resources for the common good (McClelland & Boyatzis, 1982).

Each individual possesses a unique combination of these needs, which determines their motivation and guides their career choices (McClelland, 1985, 1987).

2.2. HR Acquisition Practices: Between Formalism and Realities

Within the Cameroonian public service, acquisition is a regulated process. For secondary school teachers, this begins with training at a Teacher Training College (ENS/ENSET) and continues with formal integration as a civil servant (PCEG, PLEG, etc.). However, acquisition here specifically refers to the administrative due diligence required to integrate personnel into the State's "personnel" and "payroll" databases. This complex process involves four administrations (the user Ministry, the Ministry of Public Service, the Prime Minister's Services, and the Ministry of Finance). Current governance often results in time-consuming delays, creating fragile categories of personnel: Staff In-the-process-of-integration (ECI), personnel with integration problems (PI), or those integrated without salary coverage (ISPC).

2.3. The Concept of Sustainable Motivation

Sustainable motivation is a form of engagement (intrinsic or extrinsic) that is maintained over the long term, even when faced with obstacles (Deci & Ryan, 2000). It is based on personal interest, alignment with values (Sheldon & Elliot, 1999), and resilience (Dweck, 2006). It is fostered by clear objectives, constructive feedback (Hattie & Timperley, 2007), and a sense of competence (Deci & Ryan, 2002).

2.4. Stimulation and Development Practices

- **Stimulation Practices:** According to Deci and Ryan (1985), these aim to reinforce behaviors. They include intrinsic stimulation (autonomy, recognition), extrinsic stimulation (bonuses, promotions, feedback), and social stimulation (collaborative climate) (Bandura, 1986; Skinner, 1953).
- **Development Practices:** These focus on improving technical skills (Kolb, 1984) and transversal skills (soft skills) (Goleman, 1998). They are achieved through practical experience, mentoring (Kram, 1985), self-directed learning (Knowles, 1980), and work-life balance (Greenhaus & Allen, 2011).

2.5. Thematic Synthesis: The Relationship between HRM and Sustainable Motivation

The literature (Desimone, 2009; Hakanen et al., 2006) demonstrates that well-designed HRM is the pillar of teacher engagement. By integrating dimensions of autonomy and administrative support, institutions prevent professional burnout. Ultimately, the following links can be established:

- **Acquisition and Affiliation:** Acquisition practices (recruitment, integration) directly impact the sense of belonging. Administrative delays (ECI, PI, ISPC) undermine McClelland's **Need for Affiliation**.
- **Stimulation and Achievement:** Bonuses and recognition address the **Need for Achievement**. If compensation does not allow for a "dignified life," the psychological contract is breached, annihilating sustainable motivation.
- **Development and Power:** Continuous training and mobility allow for the acquisition of **Institutional Power**—the ability to influence one's professional environment and progress within the social and professional hierarchy.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

The present research adopts a **cross-sectional quantitative study design**. This methodological choice is justified by the objective of capturing, at a specific point in time, the state of HRM practices and analyzing their correlation with the sustainable motivation of teachers in the Mvila Department.

3.2. Sample and Data Collection Method

The study relies on a **probability sample** of 102 secondary school teachers. The recruitment of participants scrupulously respected criteria of seniority and segmental representativeness to faithfully reflect the diversity of the region's teaching body. For data collection, 120 questionnaires were distributed across the department. We recorded 102 complete and usable returns, representing a **response rate of 85%**. The distribution of respondents by grade is detailed in the table below:

Table 1: Distribution of Respondent Teachers by Grade

Grade	Headcount	Percentage
PCEG (DIPES I)	23	22,54
PLEG (DIPES II)	50	49,00
PCET (DIPET I)	6	5,88
PLET (DIPET II)	14	13,72
CPOSUP (DIPCO)	3	2,94
Autres	6	5,88
Total	102	100,0

Notes: DIPES I/II = General Secondary Education Teacher Diploma; DIPET I/II = Technical Secondary Education Teacher Diploma; DIPCO = Guidance Counselor Diploma. Source: Field Survey (2023).

3.3. Measurement of Variables

The study variables were measured using a **five-point Likert scale**, ranging from "Strongly Disagree" (1) to "Strongly Agree" (5).

- **Acquisition Practices:** Captured through concrete indicators such as the possession of the integration act and effective access to the payroll (remuneration).
- **Stimulation Practices:** Operationalized by assessing the social climate within the institution, opportunities for promotion to positions of responsibility, and the perceived value of quarterly bonuses received.
- **Development Practices:** Measured via the exercise of the right to continuous training, opportunities for professional mobility, and skill enhancement.
- **Sustainable Motivation:** Evaluated using the short version of the **Personality Research Form (PRF)** proposed by Jackson (1967). This instrument focuses on long-term commitment, attendance, and the perseverance of teachers in their pedagogical mission.

3.4. Data Analysis Technique, Validity, and Reliability

Data processing and statistical analysis were performed using **SPSS software**. The analysis was structured around two axes: a descriptive analysis of frequencies and a correlation analysis using **Pearson's correlation coefficient (r)**.

Regarding the scientific quality of the instrument:

- **Validity:** Content validity was rigorously verified by a panel of experts in educational sciences.
- **Reliability:** An internal consistency test was conducted during the pre-survey. The **Cronbach's Alpha coefficient** obtained was **0.83**, which demonstrates excellent reliability of the measurement scales (the threshold of acceptability generally being set at 0.70).

While internal consistency has been demonstrated, future research would benefit from including a systematic formal calculation on larger samples to further validate the stability of these instruments within the Cameroonian context.

4.1. Descriptive Statistics on HR Acquisition Practices

This study considers four components of Teacher HR (THR) acquisition practices: Teachers in-the-process-of-integration (ECI), those already integrated (Int), those with integration problems (PI), and those facing salary payment difficulties (ISPC).

Figure 1: Teacher Status

Source: Field survey (2023)

According to Figure 1, the majority of teachers (48.7%) are integrated, while a significant portion (36.3%) are still in the process of integration.

Figure 2: Integration via Normal Channels

Source: Field survey (2023)

Figure 2 shows that 75% of the 102 respondents in the Mvila Department were integrated through standard administrative channels.

Figure 3: Integration Difficulties Encountered

Note: PPD/O = Loss of file components/Oversight.

Figure 3 highlights that "administrative slowness" is the primary obstacle for 61% of the sample.

4.1.1. Descriptive Statistics on Stimulation Practices

Figures 4 and 5 describe practices related to performance incentives and the perception of professional status.

Figure 4: Impressions of Overall Compensation

When asked if their overall compensation (salary + benefits) was insufficient to live with dignity and nobility, 61% of teachers answered "Yes," expressing dissatisfaction with their current financial status.

Figure 5: Feelings of Devaluation and Lack of Consideration

The data shows that a majority of teachers feel devalued or socially marginalized "sometimes" or "often" due to their profession.

4.1.2. Descriptive Statistics on HR Development Practices

Figures 6 and 7 illustrate the diversification of career mobility and the importance of continuous training.

Figure 6: Diversification of Career Mobility Opportunities

Most respondents (54.3%) judge the diversification of career mobility as merely "acceptable."

Figure 7: Importance of Continuous Training at MINESEC

The majority (66.4%) perceive the importance granted to continuous training as "average."

4.1.3. Summary of results

The numerical results indicate a high level of dissatisfaction:

- Acquisition: 61% of teachers report “slowness” as a major difficulty.
- Stimulation: 61% consider their remuneration to be insufficient.
- Development: Only 11.5% consider mobility opportunities to be “good.”

4.2. Verification of Research Hypotheses

Tables 2 through 7 show the verification of hypotheses and the related correlation tests between variables.

Table 2: Contingency Table for HR1 (Acquisition)

		In your opinion, are the accompanying measures (relief costs and others) truly effective when integrating into your profession?				Total
		Yes	No	Sometimes	No idea	
The current level of sustained motivation among teachers in high schools in the Mvila department	Fair	8	19	5	4	36
	Fairly good	4	31	12	0	47
	Good	4	7	0	0	11
	Very good	4	4	0	0	08
Total		20	61	17	4	102

Source: Field survey (2023)

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Results for HR1

Symmetric measures of Pearson's R correlation test				
	Value	Asymptotic standard error	Approximate T	Approximate significance
R Pearson's R de Pearson	-0,241	0,084	-2,610	0,010
N of Valid Cases	113			

Table 5: Pearson Correlation Results for HR2 (Stimulation)

Symmetric measures of Pearson's R correlation test				
	Value	Asymptotic standard error	Approximate T	Approximate significance
R Pearson's R de Pearson	-0,371	0,079	-4,214	0,000
N of Valid Cases	113			

Table 7: Pearson Correlation Results for HR3 (Development)

Symmetric measures of Pearson's R correlation test				
	Value	Asymptotic standard error	Approximate T	Approximate significance
R Pearson's R de Pearson	-0,357	0,082	-4,024	0,000
N of Valid Cases	113			

4.2.2. Summary and Interpretation of Correlation Results

This section presents a synthesis of the statistical results. The analysis, conducted using SPSS and EXCEL, uses the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) to measure the intensity and direction of the relationship between HRM practices and sustainable motivation.

Table 8: Summary of Correlation Results

Hypotheses	Sig-R ()	Student (Calculated)	Student (Table)	(Pearson)	Decision
HR1 (Acquisition)	0,05 0,010	2,610	1,96	-0,241	Confirmed
HR2 (Stimulation)	0,05 0,000	-4,214	1,96	-0,371	Confirmed
HR3 (Développement)	0,05 0,000	4,024	1,96	-0,357	Confirmed

Statistical Analysis:

The analysis confirms all research hypotheses. The r values are all significant, revealing a decisive influence of HRM practices on teacher engagement. However, the negative direction of the correlations provides crucial insight into the realities in Mvila:

1. **H1 (Acquisition Practices):** Dysfunctions in staff integration (administrative slowness, pending files) act as a brake on motivation. As administrative delays increase, initial teacher motivation erodes.
2. **H2 (Stimulation Practices):** This is the strongest correlation in the study. The lack of tangible rewards, recognition, and adequate bonuses significantly reduces long-term commitment.
3. **H3 (Development Practices):** The lack of clear career prospects and the deficit of continuous training opportunities weigh heavily on the sustainability of motivation, preventing teachers from projecting themselves long-term in their profession.

In fine, these results demonstrate that current acquisition, stimulation, and development practices are perceived as deficient by secondary teachers in Mvila. These management gaps specifically impact the needs for **achievement, affiliation, and power**, which are the pillars of sustainable motivation.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section analyzes the results in light of the Human Relations School of thought and the study's theoretical framework, specifically **McClelland's Theory of Needs**. Regarding the link between HRM and the sustainable motivation of teachers in the Mvila Department, our work demonstrates that HRM serves as the primary driver. The confirmation of the hypotheses shows that sustainable motivation is an indispensable prerequisite for the effectiveness of the educational system. The essence of each hypothesis is discussed here by aligning it with the three fundamental needs identified by McClelland.

5.1. Acquisition Practices and the Need for Affiliation

HR acquisition is a critical process that ensures the presence of qualified personnel in adequate quantities. In Cameroon, although the State ensures recruitment through MINESUP, MINESEC, and MINFOPRA, the culmination of this process—integration—is marred by delays and irregularities (lost files, delayed employee ID numbers).

These failures erode motivation from the very start of the career. To satisfy McClelland's **Need for Affiliation**, teachers must feel like full members of the educational community. We advocate for the implementation of an accelerated and **computerized** integration process, supported by a unified digital database spanning from teacher training colleges to the various ministries. Seamless integration allows teachers to collaborate calmly with their hierarchy, reinforcing their sense of institutional belonging.

5.2. Stimulation Practices and the Need for Achievement

In this context, stimulation refers to increasing the energy and professional activity of teachers. Improving compensation is the central lever for this revitalization. Despite the Special Statute of 2000, teacher conditions remain precarious in the face of the current cost of living.

A reassessment of remuneration must not solely target the satisfaction of primary needs but must enable the attainment of the **Need for Achievement**. A motivated teacher is one who possesses the means to lead projects, produce textbooks, and contribute to curriculum reform adapted to African realities. This recognition of their capacity to produce concrete results generates long-term satisfaction—a pillar of sustainable motivation.

5.3. Development Practices and the Need for Power

HR development concerns career mobility and continuous training. While developing teachers theoretically improves performance, the importance granted to these aspects in Mvila remains average, limiting long-term perspectives.

Beyond traditional pedagogical training, we suggest that the administration offer specialized training providing high-level expertise. This increased competence allows teachers to satisfy their **Need for Institutional Power**. By acquiring professional "aura" and intellectual confidence, they become capable of occupying high-level positions of responsibility and positively influencing their professional environment.

5.4. Synthesis: The "Dissatisfaction Cycle"

The interpretation of the negative correlations reveals a "dissatisfaction cycle" specific to the local educational system. Unlike Western contexts where professional development is often the primary driver of engagement, motivation in Mvila is stifled at its foundation by fundamental failures:

- **Deficient Acquisition** creates a sense of exclusion.
- **Insufficient Stimulation** prevents any sense of achievement.

Strategic Recommendations

To break this cycle and stabilize motivation, two major actions are imperative:

1. **Full Digitalization:** Immediate implementation of a digital career tracking system at MINESEC to permanently eliminate file loss and delays in administrative processing.
2. **Statutory and Financial Revision:** Align the Special Statute of teachers with the real cost of living to guarantee the "nobility of the profession" and transform teaching into a career of achievement rather than a refuge of precarity.

6. CONCLUSION

The mission of this research was to explore the complex dynamics between Human Resource Management (HRM) and the sustainable motivation of teachers in the Mvila Department. Within a context marked by structural frustrations and permanent administrative restrictions, the study reveals that the inconsistency of current management strategies constitutes a major hindrance to professional fulfillment.

The analysis of data collected from 102 teachers demonstrates unequivocally that deficiencies in the HRM system—whether at the national or local level—fail to generate the sustained effort necessary for pedagogical excellence. If motivation is the engine that initiates and maintains effort until task completion (Levy-Leboyer, 1999), its "sustainable" dimension is the guarantor of the educational system's stability. Our results underscore that without a profound reform of acquisition and stimulation mechanisms, the risk of massive teacher disengagement will continue to weigh negatively on learner performance and the overall quality of education in Cameroon.

In sum, to transform the teaching profession into a lever for development, educational authorities must imperatively transition from a purely administrative and reactive management style to a strategic HRM approach, centered on satisfying the personnel's needs for achievement and recognition.

7. LIMITATIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

Despite the contributions of this study, several limitations must be highlighted to qualify the scope of the results:

- **Research Design:** The adoption of a cross-sectional design allows for the establishment of significant correlations but cannot be interpreted in terms of strict causality. Only a longitudinal study would allow for tracking the evolution of motivation across several career cycles.
- **Geographical Scope:** As the sample was restricted to the Mvila Department, the generalization of the results to the entire Cameroonian territory must be made with caution, given potential regional disparities.
- **Nature of the Data:** Since the data were self-reported, they may be subject to social desirability bias, although anonymity was guaranteed.

For **future research**, it would be pertinent to extend this survey to a nationally representative sample covering the ten regions of the country. Furthermore, integrating a qualitative approach (semi-structured interviews) would allow for a deeper exploration of the psychological dimensions of motivation that quantitative tools only partially capture. Finally, a comparative analysis between the public and private sectors could offer new perspectives on the effectiveness of HRM models in Cameroon.

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